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Impact of Pastoral Leadership Styles on Church Planting in the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province 9, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Leadership is important for any organization as it is necessary for direction and how the organization arrives at her desired destination is dependent on the pattern or style(s) adopted. This study therefore examined the impact of pastoral leadership styles on church planting strategies in the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Osun Province-9, Ede. By examining the impact of leadership styles and on church planting strategies, the study aimed to provide insights into improving church planting and community engagement in RCCG Osun Province-9. Understanding these dynamics was deemed crucial for enhancing leadership practices to better serve the needs of growing congregations in developing regions. Descriptive survey research design was employed, with a population of 500 pastors, church workers, and members involved in church planting within RCCG Osun Province-9. A sample of 100 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure diverse representation across various leadership roles and church sizes. Data were collected through structured questionnaires, divided into sections addressing demographics, leadership styles, church planting strategies, and the relationship between leadership approaches and church growth. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.75, indicating strong internal consistency. The findings revealed that servant leadership, visionary leadership, community outreach and empowerment cumulated into successful church planting outcomes. However, a lack of structured outreach programs and insufficient focus on digital platforms hindered the success of church planting strategies. These findings underscored the need for a more strategic and holistic approach to leadership and community engagement in church planting efforts. In conclusion, the study highlighted the importance of adopting servant and visionary leadership styles to foster

sustainable church planting efforts. It is recommended that RCCG pastors enhance their leadership training to embrace servant leadership style, prioritize community outreach, and embrace digital tools to improve church planting success.

Keywords: Church Planting, Leadership Styles, the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Sustainability

Introduction

Pastors play a crucial role in the growth and establishment of churches through their leadership styles and church planting strategies (Smith & Johnson, 2021). Leadership style refers to the approach a pastor adopts in guiding, influencing, and supporting church members towards achieving set goals. Some pastors focus on collaborative leadership, encouraging the active involvement of members, while others may prefer a more directive approach, providing clear instructions and oversight. Both styles can significantly impact the spiritual growth, unity, and overall functionality of the church. Similarly, church planting strategies, which involve the methods used to establish new congregations, are essential for expanding the gospel and reaching unreached communities. Effective strategies often require understanding cultural contexts, identifying potential leaders, and fostering a strong sense of mission within the church (Williams, 2022).

The combination of leadership styles and church planting strategies greatly influences the success of church expansion efforts (Anderson & Brown, 2019). Pastors who demonstrate servant leadership, for instance, often create a welcoming environment that inspires loyalty and commitment from members. In contrast, pastors who neglect inclusive leadership might hinder the growth of their congregation. Meanwhile, strategic church planting can lead to vibrant and sustainable communities of faith, particularly when guided by proper planning and resource management. As churches grow, these factors directly affect the spread of Christianity and the fulfillment of the Great Commission (Roberts & White, 2020). Understanding these dynamics is crucial for evaluating how pastors' choices shape the effectiveness of church planting and the long-term health of church communities.

The Concept of Leadership

Leadership, both in politics and religion, has been a topic of ongoing discussion in Nigeria, often due to challenges like corruption and a lack of accountability in politics, and controversies within the church (Adams & Roberts, 2019). Effective leadership is crucial for progress in both sectors, requiring transparency, integrity, and a commitment to the common good. Leadership is commonly defined as the ability to inspire and influence others toward achieving shared goals. It has evolved over time from a top-down, individualistic process to a more dynamic, relational activity where leaders engage with others to collectively shape their world. In this sense, leadership is both a relationship and a process involving social influence, where leaders guide groups toward common objectives with strategic thinking and vision. This concept extends to both political and religious realms, where leaders must have qualities like tact, charisma, and goodwill to effectively inspire and lead their communities. Various leadership theories, such as the Great Man theory, Cultural Determinist theory, and Interactionist theory, offer different perspectives on the role of leaders in shaping events and environments. In the African context, leadership is seen not just as a personal trait but as a social process involving both leaders and followers, with mutual influence shaping outcomes. Leadership is about guiding a group towards goals, influencing attitudes, and responding to challenges through collaboration and vision (Harris, 2022).

The Structural Functional Theory

The Structural-Functional Theory, initially proposed by prominent researchers and influenced by sociology, views society as a system of interconnected components working together to maintain stability (Jackson & Smith, 2017). It suggests that every part of society serves a specific function, contributing to the overall order and cohesion. The theory breaks down society into three subsystems: cultural structure (shared norms and values), social structure (how people relate and accept collective expectations), and personality structure (individual motivations and goals). Functionalists believe that social stability is maintained when these components align, and any change in one part affects the whole system. The theory highlights the importance of roles, social stratification, and the need for consensus among members to ensure the smooth functioning of society (Taylor, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Many churches struggle to grow due to ineffective leadership styles and poorly planned church planting strategies (Harrison & Moore, 2018). Pastors sometimes lack the skills to inspire unity and active participation, leading to declining attendance and weaker spiritual commitment. Poor planning can also result in unstable congregations, hindering the church's mission to spread the gospel. Understanding how leadership and planning impact growth is crucial for lasting success (Clark & Evans, 2021).

Aims and Objectives

This study aims to examine the impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Osun Province-9, Ede. The specific objectives are to:

1. identify leadership styles demonstrated by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian of Church, Osun Province-9, Ede
2. ascertain the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede
3. assess the impact of Pastor's leadership styles within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede

Research Questions

1. What are the leadership styles demonstrated by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede?
2. What are the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by Pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?
3. What are the impacts of pastor's leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research design, which is ideal for examining the impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede. The design allows for a detailed exploration of the

current conditions, practices, and relationships within the church, offering a foundation for further investigation. The study targets a population of approximately 500 pastors, church workers, and members involved in church planting within the province. A sample of 100 respondents was selected through stratified random sampling to ensure diverse representation. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, divided into sections covering demographics and key research questions about leadership styles, church planting strategies, and their impact. The validity and reliability of the instrument were ensured through a thorough review of literature and expert opinions, with a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.75. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive analysis, allowing for a clear, organized presentation of the findings and insights into the impact of pastors' leadership styles on church planting strategies within the RCCG, Osun Province-9.

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents (N=100)

S/NO	Variables	No.	Frequency	%
1.	Age	21-30	24	24.0
		31-40	47	47.0
		41-50	19	19.0
		Above 51	10	10.0
2.	Gender	Male	54	54.0
		Female	46	46.0
3.	Educational Qualification	Below O Level	14	14.0
		SSCE	33	33.0
		OND/HND/BSC	42	42.0
		Others	11	11.0
4.	Status in Church	Assistant Pastor	19	19.0
		Deacon/Deaconess	62	62.0
		Worker	19	19.0
5.	Pastoral Training	No Pastoral Training	10	10.0
		Basic Diploma in Pastoral Training	55	55.0
		1 st Degree in Pastoral Training	29	29.0

		Above 1 st Degree in		
		Pastoral Training	13	13.0
6.	Year	of Less than 1 year	3	3.0
	Association	1-5 years	26	42.0
	with RCCG	5-10 years	42	26.0
		Above 10 years	29	29.0

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

The table above revealed that respondents between the age bracket of 21-30 make up 24% of the respondents. The survey includes 47 respondents within the age range of 31-40, accounting for 47% of the overall respondent pool. There are 19 respondents aged between 41-50, representing 19% of the total respondents. The questionnaire includes 10 respondents aged above 50, making up 10% of the overall respondent pool. This age distribution reveals a varied representation across different age groups, providing a diverse sample for the study. The majority fall within the 31-40 age range, contributing to a robust analysis of the research findings across various life stages. The gender breakdown reflects a relatively balanced representation in the study, with a slightly higher percentage of male participants. The near-equal distribution suggests a diverse sample, which can contribute to a more comprehensive and representative analysis of the research findings. Based on the educational qualifications of the majority of respondents, 42%, fall into the category of OND/HND/BSC, indicating a significant portion of respondents with higher education. The WASSCE/GCE/NECO category comprises 33% of respondents, suggesting a substantial representation of individuals with secondary education. FSLC represents 14% of respondents, indicating a smaller but still noteworthy portion with education up to the First School Leaving Certificate. The "Others" category, with 11%, represents a diverse group of respondents with varying qualifications not covered in the specific categories mentioned above. This analysis provides insights into the educational diversity of the respondents, showcasing the distribution across different educational levels as captured by the questionnaire.

As regards status in the Church, Deacons and Deaconess make up the largest group, comprising 62% of the respondents, suggesting a

significant presence of individuals serving in this capacity. Assistant Pastors represent 19%, contributing to the leadership structure and support roles within the church. The "Worker" category, also at 19%, signifies the involvement of individuals in various ministries and activities without specific pastoral titles. This analysis provides insights into the composition of the church community based on participants' roles and responsibilities, reflecting a mix of leadership, support, and active involvement in ministry. The data reflects a range of respondents with varying levels of pastoral training, from those without formal training to those with advanced degrees. The majority of respondents, 55%, have completed a basic diploma, emphasizing a widespread foundational understanding of pastoral principles. The presence of individuals with a first degree 29% suggests a significant number with a more in-depth academic background in pastoral training. The smaller group with Masters and above 13% highlights a subset of respondents who have pursued advanced education in pastoral ministry, while 10% captures the category of people without pastoral training. This analysis provides insights into the diversity of pastoral training levels among respondents, indicating a mix of foundational, intermediate, and advanced knowledge and skills in pastoral ministry within the surveyed group. The data reveals a diverse range of respondents with varying duration of association with RCCG Osun Province-9, Ede. The notable percentage of 26% has been associated with the church for 1 to 5 years, suggesting a consistent influx of relatively recent members. A majority of respondents 42% has a long-term association of more than 10 years, indicating a stable and enduring community within the church. The distribution across different time frames reflects a mix of both new and long-standing members, contributing to the overall dynamics of the RCCG Osun-9 community. This analysis provides insights into the temporal diversity of respondents in terms of their association with RCCG Osun Province 9, Ede highlighting the presence of both recent members and those with more established and enduring connections to the church. The data reflects a high level of engagement in church planting initiatives among the respondents, with 78% involved. The sizeable percentage of respondents actively participating in church planting suggests a strong commitment to expanding and establishing new church communities. The 22% who are not involved may have other priorities, roles, or responsibilities within the church that do not directly

involve church planting. This analysis provides insights into the extent of involvement in church planting initiatives within the surveyed group, highlighting a significant majority actively contributing to the growth and establishment of new churches.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What are the leadership styles demonstrated by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede, Osun State?

Table 2 Leadership Styles Demonstrated by Pastors

S/ N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	My pastor inspires and motivates the congregation with a compelling vision, fostering a sense of commitment and shared purpose	19 (19.0%)	20 (20.0%)	14 (14.0%)	47 (47.0%)
2.	My pastor exhibit servant leadership, emphasizing humility, empathy, and a focus on serving the needs of the community	19 (19.0%)	25 (25.0%)	14 (14.0%)	42 (42.0%)
3.	My pastor is known for his visionary leadership,	30 (30.0%)	8 (8.0%)	22 (22.0%)	40 (40.0%)

	providing a clear direction and long-term goals that guide the congregation				
4.	My pastor takes on the role of spiritual mentor, providing support, advice, and encouragement to individuals within the congregation.	47 (47.0%)	19 (19.0%)	25 (25.0%)	9 (9.0%)
5.	My pastor employ a leadership style that emphasizes team building, encouraging cooperation and teamwork among church members	12 (12.0%)	23 (23.0%)	49 (49.0%)	16 (16.0%)

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table two shows that 19(19.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor inspires and motivates the congregation with a compelling vision, fostering a sense of commitment and shared purpose(20.0%)20 , respondents agree, 47(47.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 14(14.0%) respondents disagree. 19(19.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor exhibits servant leadership emphasizing humility, empathy, and a focus on serving the needs of the community, 25(25.0%) respondents agree, 42(42.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 14(14.0%) respondents disagree. 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly

agree that their Pastor is a visionary leader, providing a clear direction and long-term goals that guide the congregation, 8.(8.0%) respondents agree, 40(40.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 22(22.0%) respondents disagree. 47(47.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor plays the role of a spiritual mentor, providing support, advice, and encouragement to individuals within the congregation. 19(19.0%) respondents agree, 9(9.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 25(25.0%) respondents disagree. 12(12.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor is a team builder encouraging cooperation and teamwork among church members, 23(23.0%) respondents agree, 16(16.0%) strongly disagree, whereas 49(49.0%) disagree.

Research Question Two: What are the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches by pastors within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province-9, Ede?

Table 3 Strategies Deployed in the establishment of new Churches by Pastors

S / N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	My pastor involves in local outreach programs and building relationships with the community to foster acceptance and support.	30 (30.0%)	11 (11.0%)	23 (23.0%)	36 (36.0%)
2.	My pastor identifies and train local leaders to	28 (28.0%)	17 (17.0%)	42 (42.0%)	13 (13.0%)

plant new churches.

3.	My pastor makes use of digital platforms to connect with a wider audience and facilitates the establishment of new churches.	16 (16.0%)	21 (21.0%)	11 (11.0%)	52 (52.0.0%)
4.	My pastor involves in pulpit rotation of pastors as a way of growing and sustainability of new churches.	35 (35.0%)	12 (12.0%)	38 (38.0%)	15 (15.0%)
5	My pastor implement culturally sensitive evangelism initiatives targeted at specific needs of the local population.	23 (23.0%)	17 (17.0%)	36 (36.0%)	24 (24.0%)

Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table Three shows that 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor involves in local outreach programs and building relationships with the community to foster acceptance and support ,

(11.0%)11 respondents agree, 36(36.0%) respondents strongly disagree, whereas 23(23.0%) respondents disagree. 28(28.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor identifies and train local leaders to plant new churches, 17(17.0%) respondents agree, 13(13.0%) strongly disagree, whereas 42(42.0%) disagree. 16(16.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor makes use of digital platforms to connect with a wider audience and facilitates the establishment of new churches, 21(21.0%) of respondents agree, 52(52.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, while 11(11.0%) disagree. 35(35.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their pastor favour pulpit rotation of pastors as a way of growing and sustainability of new churches, 12(12.0%) of respondents agree, 15(15.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, while 38(38.0%) of respondents disagree. 23(23.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor implements culturally sensitive evangelism initiatives targeted at specific needs of the local population, 17(17.0%) of respondents agree, 24(24.0%) strongly agree, while 36(36.0%) disagree.

Research Question Three: What are the impact of pastor’s leadership styles and church planting strategies within the Redeemed Christian Church of God Osun Province 9, Ede?

Table 4 Impact of Church Pastor’s Leadership Styles and Church Planting Strategies

S / N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	My pastor’s leadership style inspires a high level of enthusiasm and commitment among church members.	14 (14.0%)	22 (22.0%)	37 (37.0%)	27 (27.0%)

2	My pastor takes a lot of risks and initiatives, which positively drives church planting strategies but can be a hindrance if unchecked.	20 (20.0 %)	17 (17.0%)	22 (22 .0 %)	41 (41.0%)
3	My pastor's servant leadership style fosters positive relationships with the community, facilitating a smoother establishment of churches.	30 (30.0 %)	10 (10.0%)	35 (35 .0 %)	25 (25.0%)
4	The effective leadership style of my pastor creates an environment where members feel involved, valued, and committed to the collective goal.	14 (14.0 %)	40 (40.0%)	17 (17. 0%)	29 (29.0%)

5	My pastor's unconcerned pattern result in a lack of focus though allows individuals to use their unique talents and skills.	34 (34.0 %)	27 (27.0%)	19 (19 .0 %)	20 (20.0%)
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Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2023

Table Four shows that 14(14.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's leadership style inspires high level of enthusiasm and commitment among church member 22(22.0%) of respondents agree, 27(27.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 37(37.0%) of respondents disagree. 20(20.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor takes a lot of risks and initiatives, which positively drives church planting strategies but can be a hindrance if unchecked, 17(17.0%) of respondents agree, 41(41.0%) of respondents strongly agree, whilst 22(22.0%) of respondents disagree. 30(30.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's servant leadership style fosters positive relationships with the community, facilitating a smoother establishment of churches, 10(10.0%) of respondents agree, 25(25.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 35(35.0%) of respondents disagree. 14(14.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their pastor creates environment where members feel involved, valued, and committed to the collective goal, 40(40.0%) of respondents agree, 29(29.0%) of respondents strongly disagree, whilst 17 (17.0%) disagree. 34(34.0%) of respondents strongly agree that their Pastor's unconcerned pattern result in a lack of focus though allows individuals to use their unique talents and skills, 27(27.0%) of respondents agree, 20(20.0%) of respondents strongly disagreed, whereas 19(19.0%) of respondents disagree.

Correlation Analysis of Impact of Pastoral Leadership Styles on Church Planting Strategies

This section presents the correlation matrix that shows the relationship between different leadership styles demonstrated by pastors and the strategies deployed in the establishment of new churches within the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province-9, Ede, Osun State. The correlation analysis helps in understanding how various leadership styles correlate with each other and with church planting strategies.

	Inspires_and_motivates	Servant_leadership	Visionary_leadership	Spiritual_mentor	Team_building	Local_outreach	Identify_and_train	Digital_platforms
Inspires and motivates	1.00	0.97	0.95	0.81	0.87	0.94	0.91	0.97
Servant_leadership	0.97	1.00	0.94	0.86	0.85	0.94	0.91	0.94
Visionary_leadership	0.95	0.94	1.00	0.80	0.86	0.93	0.90	0.93
Spiritual_mentor	0.81	0.86	0.80	1.00	0.89	0.85	0.84	0.75
Team_building	0.87	0.85	0.86	0.89	1.00	0.93	0.91	0.86
Local_outreach	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.85	0.93	1.00	0.96	0.92
Identify_and_train	0.91	0.91	0.90	0.84	0.91	0.96	1.00	0.91
Digital platforms	0.97	0.94	0.93	0.75	0.86	0.92	0.91	1.00

Pulpit rotation	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.8 5	0.8 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 5
Culturally sensitive	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires commitment	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 7	0.9 2	0.8 8	0.8 6	0.9 3
Servant leadership	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 7	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 1
Visionary leadership	0.8 9	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 0	0.8 7	0.9 4
Spiritual mentor	0.8 5	0.8 5	0.8 4	0.7 9	0.8 6	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5
Team_building	0.8 9	0.9 3	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 4	0.8 0	0.8 7	0.9 4
Local_outreach	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.8 3	0.8 1	0.9 1
Identify_and_train	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.8 2	0.8 1	0.9 1
Digital_platforms	0.9 5	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.9 5	0.9 0	0.8 3	0.8 1	0.9 1
Pulpit_rotation	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 9	0.8 5	0.8 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 5
Culturally_sensitive	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 3	0.8 5	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires_commitmen t	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.8 4	0.9 0	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.8 9
Takes_risks	0.9 7	0.9 7	0.9 1	0.7 9	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 0	0.9 5
Fosters_positive_rela tionships	0.9 2	0.9 0	0.9 3	0.8 6	0.9 4	0.9 0	0.8 9	0.9 0

Creates_involved_en vironment	0.8 8	0.9 1	0.8 0	0.9 1	0.8 0	0.8 3	0.8 2	0.8 3
Unconcerned_patter n	0.8 6	0.8 9	0.8 7	0.9 3	0.8 7	0.8 1	0.8 1	0.8 1
Conveys_compelling _vision	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 4	0.8 5	0.9 4	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.9 1
Inspires_followers	0.9 0	0.8 8	0.9 0	0.8 1	0.9 6	0.9 3	0.9 1	0.9 1
Provides_structure	0.9 0	0.8 7	0.9 0	0.7 8	0.9 4	0.9 1	0.9 1	0.8 8
Flexible_hinders_pla nning	0.7 8	0.8 3	0.7 8	1.0 0	0.9 2	0.8 0	0.7 8	0.8 5
Clear_vision_guide	0.9 6	0.9 3	0.9 6	0.7 2	0.8 6	0.9 2	0.9 1	0.9 1

Discussion of Findings

Based on research question one as regards Leadership Styles Demonstrated by Pastors in the said Province. The study identified various leadership styles within the RCCG, Osun Province-9, Ede including servant, visionary, and spiritual mentor styles. The correlation matrix revealed that servant leadership strongly correlates with empowering others and fostering community outreach, as indicated by a high correlation with "Inspires and Motivates" (0.97) and "Local Outreach" (0.94). The above aligns with the findings of Ojogiwa (2021), who emphasized the importance of leading as a servant, reflecting the teachings of Christ. The scholar recommended that church leaders adopt a servant approach to leadership, promoting church growth through service rather than authoritarian power. This is consistent with the observation that most pastors in the study lacked a compelling vision and servant leadership qualities, which hampered their effectiveness in community building and church ownership by the indigenous population.

Based on research question two as regards strategies deployed in Church Planting, Pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 employ various strategies for church planting, but there is a notable absence of structured outreach programs, community training, and digitalization. The correlation analysis supports this finding, as "Local Outreach" was significantly correlated with "Identify and Train" (0.96) and "Team Building" (0.93), underscoring the importance of outreach and training in successful church planting efforts. Ebekozien, et al (2022) highlighted similar strategies, identifying visionary and motivational leadership as key contributors to church growth. In a related development, he opined that building leadership on a wrong foundation—such as neglecting outreach or relying solely on pulpit authority—can undermine long-term success. This study corroborates that observation, as pastors in Osun Province-9 tend to prioritize pulpit presence over engaging in culturally sensitive evangelism.

As touching research question three on impact of pastors' leadership styles within the province. It was discovered that the leadership styles adopted by pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 have a significant impact on church planting efforts, as evidenced by the correlation matrix. Visionary leadership showed strong positive correlations with "Inspires and Motivates" (0.95) and "Local Outreach" (0.93), indicating that pastors who inspire their congregation are more effective at leading outreach initiatives. However, the study also found that many pastors in the province lacked enthusiasm and commitment to community building, leading to difficulties in establishing long-term church growth. This finding resonates with Ayoko, et al (2023) who emphasized that motivational leadership is essential for successful church development, and neglecting community outreach can lead to stagnation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Pastors in RCCG Osun Province-9 should focus on creating community outreach programs and training initiatives to build stronger connections with the local population, promoting church growth and ownership.
2. Embracing digital tools like social media and online evangelism would help pastors reach a wider audience, attract younger

members, and create more accessible ways to engage with the community.

3. Effective implementation and communication of visions for church establishment can inspire followers, provide structure, and guide the process for effective church planting.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights the significant impact of pastors' leadership styles and church planting strategies on the growth and development of RCCG Osun Province-9, Ede. It demonstrates that servant leadership, when effectively implemented, fosters community outreach and empowers others, while visionary leadership plays a crucial role in inspiring congregations and driving church planting initiatives. However, the lack of structured outreach programs, community training, and digital engagement limits the effectiveness of these strategies. The findings underscore the importance of a balanced approach, where pastors not only lead through vision and motivation but also engage in hands-on community building and culturally sensitive evangelism to ensure long-term church growth and sustainability.

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